

IUC 07: Beyond 3D: Tools for tracking spatiotemporal microstructure evolution

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Spatiotemporal microstructure data are the key results of continuum full-field and atomic-scale computer simulations and cutting-edge diffraction microscopy experiments. Typically represented as voxel, point, line, or triangularized meshes, these data cover a variety of materials information and their embedding into three-dimensional field quantities. The large variety of computer codes for spatiotemporal microstructure simulation limits interoperability and repurposeability between different tools. Therefore, Infrastructure Use Case (IUC) 07 of NFDI MatWerk aims at developing a flexible standard for (meta-) data representation of time-dependent microstructures. Proof-of-concept workflows are developed, which exemplify how such description and ontology connection can be exported from existent MSE simulation tools.

Figure 1: Example of a polycrystalline microstructure represented as voxels on a regular mesh. The grain orientations are color coded with respect to the inverse pole figure

The primary objectives of IUC 07 revolve around the development and implementation of workflows and standards for managing material point data, facilitating microstructure evolution modeling, and ensuring compatibility across various tools. The first goal is to create general and well-documented data standards for the automated documentation of time-dependent material point data, which

includes information on phases, grain orientations, distortions, temperatures, etc. These data standards will be implemented in workflows to enable efficient data management and retrieval across various existing simulation tools, as for example OpenPhase¹, DAMASK², and Kanapy³. pyiron⁴, the integrated development environment (IDE) for computational materials science, allows the seamless connection of several tools for modeling and post-processing the evolution of microstructures in a coherent workflow. This will streamline the process of analyzing microstructural changes over time.

A significant part of the project involves establishing a comprehensive metadata format for time-dependent microstructure data. This format needs to be compatible with a representative set of tools and flexible enough to support various serialization strategies, such as YAML, JSON, and HDF5. To facilitate the use of this new standard across different platforms, a suite of format converters (parsers) will be developed for relevant software tools used in simulating microstructure evolution. Integration with existing open-source software is crucial for the project's success. The developed parsers will be embedded into widely used software packages like DAMASK, Kanapy, OpenPhase, and pyiron, ensuring broad adoption and utility.

To demonstrate the advantages of the new data format, example workflows and demonstrators will be implemented. These will showcase the practical benefits and improvements brought about by the standardized format and integrated workflows. Additionally, the project will augment voxel information with XFEM-like sub-structures, providing more detailed and accurate representations of interfaces and grain boundaries. Methods for polygonizing homogeneous structures, such as grains and phases, will also be developed and integrated, further enhancing the capability of microstructure simulations.

By achieving these goals, the project aims to streamline the management of material point data and enhance the capabilities of microstructure evolution simulations. The development of a standardized, flexible data format and integrated workflows will facilitate more efficient and accurate simulations, benefiting researchers and engineers working in the field of materials science.

Features of a Standardized Format for Spatiotemporal Microstructure Description

- Transferable data format to store time-series of discretized microstructures (voxels, finite elements) to represent voxelized data on different layers and physical quantities: phase, grain orientation, temperature, distortions, defects, etc.
- Support by DAMASK, Kanapy, OpenPhase, and pyiron
- Rigorous documentation of concepts, constraints and semantic connections to other existing ontologies of the format to support convertibility to other frequently used file formats.
- Adequate microstructure description along the whole process-chain

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¹ <https://www.openphase.rub.de>

² <https://damask.mpie.de>

³ <https://github.com/ICAMS/Kanapy.git>

⁴ <https://pyiron.org>